

SYNTACTIC CATEGORY AND ITS FUNCTIONS

Antonio Constantino Soares

Master Program of Linguistics, Udayana University
antonio.soares.281170@gmail.com
Bali, Indonesia

Abstract

This research described about the "Syntactic Category and its Functions" of English language which only implemented on the "present tense". This research was more focused on some certain sentences elements and expanded into some type of verbs such as ordinary intransitive, complex-intransitive, semitransitive, ordinary monotransitive, complex-transitive, ditransitive and prepositional partial of ditransitive. This research was intended to increase the English learners and teachers' abilities to have a better understanding related to the sentence elements of English language in the future time. The theories of syntax proposed by Huddleston and Pullum (2005) and Verhaar (2012) were applied to determine the syntax category and its functions in this research. The introspective reflexive method was applied to gain the data in this research, however the qualitative descriptive method was applied to analyse the data in this research.

Key words: syntactic, category, function, English language

BACKGROUND

English language is one of the Indo-European language groups and typologically, it belongs to the Accusative languages with SVO word order. English language is also officially spoken as the first language in five main countries such as the United Kingdom, the United States, Australia, New Zealand and Canada. Besides being a first language for the five countries above, English is also spoken as the second language in some Europe countries such as the Netherlands, France, Germany, Spain, Denmark and, etc.

However, English is learned just as the foreign language in Asia countries generally and in Southeast Asia countries particularly. Today, English is the most needed because of the globalization era and everyone is demanded to be able to speak English well. This reason is also based on Huddleston and Pullum's statement (2005:1) that English is probably the most widely used language in the world, with around 400 million native speakers and a similar number of bilingual speakers in several dozen partially English-speaking countries, and hundreds of million more users in other countries where English is widely known and used in business, government, or media. Today, people learn the English

language as the foreign language because of having different purposes and different needs. They learn the English language because they want to study and work in overseas countries, or because of the other demands. Some learners still face some obstacles to learn the English language because both students and teachers have not been able to differentiate what Syntactic Category and Function are. Every English clause always consists of three main elements namely Category, Function and Role. Verhaar (2012:162) states that there are three ways to analyse a clause syntactically. First, "There are functions" in the clause and every clause has their own roles semantically as well.

METHODOLOGY AND THEORIES

The data used in this paper just consist of a few parts of “simple present tense” which expanded into some clauses such as ordinary intransitive, complex-intransitive, ordinary-monotransitive, complex-transitive, semitransitive ditransitive and prepositional partial of ditransitive. Maclin (1996:334) states that the present tense can be used in several ways. It does not always show what is happening now, as you would think from its name. The theory of Syntax proposed by Huddleston and Pullum (2005) and the theory of Verhaar (2012) were applied in this research. Verhaar (2012:161) also states that syntax is a grammar that discusses the relation between word in utterances. The Introspectivereflexive method was used to gain the data in this research, however the qualitative descriptive method was used to analyse the data. Quirk (1973:12) also states that a sentence may alternatively be seen as comprising five units called elements of sentence.

Huddleston and Pullum (2005:78) propose five canonical clause structures syntactically. They are as follow:

NAME STRUCTURE		
I. Ordinary Intransitive	S-P	
II. Complex- Intransitive	S-P-PC	we felt happy.
III. Ordinary-Mono Transitive	S-P-Od	we sold our house.
IV. Complex-Transitive	S-P-Od-PC	we made them happy.
V. Ditransitive	S-P-Oi-Od	we gave them some food.

DISCUSSION

The following data are the examples of ordinary intransitive and complex-intransitive clauses.

1. *You walk.*
PRN.S V1.ØMP
2. *She feels sad.*
PRN.S V1.MP ADJ/PC

Categorilly, the data on the clause (1) above consist of a second plural pronoun and an intransitive verb.

Grammatically, *you* behaves as the only subject as the sole argument, however *walk* functions as the predicate. The time modifier of “Simple Present Tense” such as *every day, every morning, every evening, every week and, etc* are considered as optionals. They can be applied based on the semantics role. The data on the clause (2) categorilly consist of a third singular pronoun, an intransitive verb, an adjective. Syntactically, *she* behaves as the subject grammatical, *feels* functions as the predicate and *sad* functions as the predicate complement.

The following data are the examples of semitransitive clauses.

3. *We drink.*
PRN.S V1.ØMP
4. *The dog catches every day.*
NP.S V1.MP NP.TM
5. *A cow eats in the field every day.*
NP/S V1.MP PP.PM NP.TM

Categorilly, the clause on the data (3) above consist of a first plural pronoun and a transitive verb without an object voice (OV) because the position of (OV) here is not optional. Syntactically, *we* behaves as the subject grammatical, and *drink* is an transitive verb and functions as the unmark predicate. The data on the clause (4) consist of a noun phrase, a mark predicate, and a noun phrase. Syntactically, *The dog* behaves as the subject, *catches* functions as the mark predicate, *every day* functions as the time modifier. The data on the clause (5) consist of a noun phrase, a transitive verb, a prepositional phrase and a noun phrase. Syntactically, *a cow* behaves as the subject grammatical, *eat* functions as the predicate, *in the field* functions as the place modifier and *every day* functions as the time modifier.

The following data are the examples of ordinary monotransitive and complex-transitive clauses.

6. *We drink tea every evening.*
PRN.S V1.P N.O NP.TM
7. *The man makes us angry.*

NP.S V1.MP PRN.D.O
ADJ.PC

The data on the clause (6) consist of a first plural pronoun, a monotransitive verb, a noun and a noun phrase. Syntactically, *we* behaves as the subject grammatical, *drink* functions as the predicate, *tea* functions as the direct object and *every evening* functions as the time modifier. The data on the clause (7) consists of a noun phrase, a complex-transitive verb, a first plural pronoun and an adjective. Syntactically, *the man* behaves as the subject grammatical, *makes* functions as the main predicate, *us* functions as the indirect object and *angry* functions as the predicate complement.

The following data are the examples of ditransitive clauses

8. *They give her a book.*

PRN.S V1.ØMP PRN.I.O
NP.D.O

9. *She buys us pens.*

PRN.S V1.MP PRN.I.O
NP.D.O

Categorically, the data on the clause (8) consist of a third subject of plural pronoun, a ditransitive verb, a third singular of object pronoun and a noun phrase. Syntactically, *they* behaves as the subject grammatical, *give* functions as the predicate, *her* functions as the indirect object, and *a book* functions as the direct object. Categorically, the data on the clause (9) consist of a third subject of singular pronoun, a ditransitive verb, a first object of plural pronoun and a noun phrase. Grammatically, *she* behaves as the subject, *buys* functions as the predicate, *us* functions as the indirect object and *pens* function as the direct object.

The following data are the examples of preposition partial of ditransitive clauses.

10. *They give a book to her.*

PRN.S V1.ØMP NP.D.O
PP.C

11. *She buys the cars for him.*

PRN.S V1.MP NP.D.O
PP.C

Categorically, the data on the clause (10) consist of a third plural of subject pronoun, a ditransitive verb, a noun phrase, a prepositional phrase. Grammatically, *they* behaves as the subject, *give* functions as the predicate, *a book* functions as the direct object and *to her* functions as the prepositional phrase of complement. Categorically, the data on the clause (11) consists of a third singular of subject pronoun, a ditransitive verb, a noun phrase and a prepositional phrase. Grammatically, *she* behaves as the subject, *give* functions as the predicate, *the cars* function as the direct object and *for her* functions as the prepositional phrase of complement.

CONCLUSION

After the data were analysed based on the theory of syntax applied, here with could be concluded that there are two main clauses that were analysed syntactically in this research. Those are intransitive clause and transitive clause. The intransitive clause was expanded into ordinary intransitive and complex-intransitive clause. The transitive clause could also be expanded into ordinary monotransitive and complex-transitive clause, ditransitive, prepositional partial of ditransitive clause, the semitransitive clauses and the prepositional partial of ditransitive clause. Most sentences always consist of categories and their grammatical functions, therefore the glosses were given to every clause to determine the categories and their grammatical functions in this research. The verbal of some certain sentences of "present tense" were used as the main data in this research because they are considered as the most difficult for the English learners.

Abbreviations of grammatical terms

ADJ	=	Adjective
C	=	Complement
D.O	=	Direct object
I.O	=	Indirect object
M	=	Mark
MP	=	Mark predicate
NP	=	Noun phrase
O	=	Object
N	=	Noun
P	=	Predicate
PC	=	Predicate complement
PPC	=	Prepositional phrase complement
PP	=	Prepositional phrase
PM	=	Place modifier
PRN	=	Pronoun
S	=	Subject
TM	=	Time modifier
V	=	Verb
Vt	=	Transitive verb
Vi	=	Intransitive verb

REFERENCES

- Maclin, A. (1996). *Reference Guide to English: A Handbook of English as a Second Language*. Dekalb College.
- Verhaar.J.W.M. (2012). *Asas-Asas Linguistik Umum*.Gadjah Mada University Press.
- Huddleston & Pullum. (2005). *A Student's Introduction to English Grammar*. Cambridge University Press.
- Quirk, R. (1973). *A University of Grammar*. Longman